

A STUDY OF CALCIUM-BARIUM ION EXCHANGE EQUILIBRIUM WITH THE HELP OF MEMBRANE ELECTRODES

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The membrane electrodes having different mobility ratios for the same pair of cations have been utilised for the determination of individual cationic activity in a mixture. The same procedure has been applied to the study of the clay system:

to measure the a_{Ca} and a_{Ba} in the solution and clay phases of both the forward and backward reactions. The variation of a_{Ca} rises sharply with added barium ions in both the forward and backward reactions, but near about the symmetry concentration, the rise is less marked, after which there is again a sharp rise. Increase of a_{Ba} even in the forward reaction is not so marked, probably because of greater adsorbability of barium ions compared to calcium.

Assuming the mass action law to hold good, the equilibrium constants of the reversible reactions have been calculated. For the determination of individual cationic activity of the solid phase as well as of the solution phases, these have been separated from each other by centrifugation. The solid phase is then redispersed after removal of free electrolytes. The values of the equilibrium constants, thus calculated from the observed activities, are found to vary somewhat with the concentration of the added electrolytes. It may, however, be noted that the calculated activities are rather sensitive functions of the observed E.M.F.

The use of clay-membrane electrodes, sensitive to divalent cations, has made possible studies of exchange equilibrium between calcium and barium ions in clays by means of ionic activity determination in a binary mixture (Marshall, "Colloid Chemistry of Silicate Minerals", 1949; Chatterjee and Marshall, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 51, 671). The method of measuring individual ion-activity in a mixture of the two, employing clay-membrane electrodes, has been outlined in previous communications (Bose, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1955, 3, 65, 109; 1957, 5, 141; 1958, 6, 233). In the present paper the mobility ratios of calcium and barium ions have been evaluated using different types of membranes, some of which have subsequently been used for the determination of activity of each of these ions in a mixture of the two. The following exchange equilibrium reaction involving calcium and barium ions has been studied on the basis of ion-activity measurements:

For this purpose activities of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions have been determined in the clay as well as in the solution phases, after separating them by centrifugation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedures regarding preparation, testing and determination of E. M. F., etc. are exactly the same as described earlier (Bose, *loc. cit.*). From the observed E.M.F. between barium chloride and a mixture of calcium and barium

chlorides of known ionic activities, placed on the two sides of the membrane electrodes, the mobility ratio is calculated by means of the simplified relationship :

$$E_{obs} = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_{Ba}^I}{a_{Ba}^{II} + a_{Ca}^{II} \cdot \frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Ba}}}$$

where E_{obs} is the observed E.M.F., a_{Ba}^I , a_{Ba}^{II} and a_{Ca}^{II} are the known barium and calcium ion activities, and U_{Ca}/U_{Ba} is the mobility ratio. The calculated mobility ratio for a number of clay-membrane electrodes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Inside $a_{Ba} = 0.0027$, Outside $a_{Ba} = 0.0009$, $a_{Ca} = 0.0003$.

*Membrane.	E.M.F.	U_{Ca}/U_{Ba}^{**}
A. A.C.6 (4)	10.5 mv	0.967
B. T.C.6 (2)	10.0	1.257
C. K.H.5	13.5	0.138
D. K.C.5	11.5	0.680

* The membranes A, B, C & D are respectively prepared from Akli, Tinpahari and Kashmir clay.

The mobility ratios, U_{Ca}/U_{Ba} , for different membrane electrodes somewhat vary with the activity range of the cations. For subsequent calculation of activities in mixtures of the ions, those values of mobility ratios have been employed as are close to the range of the measured activities. In order to evaluate the individual activities of the ions in a mixture, it is necessary to use, as already mentioned earlier (Bose, *loc.cit.*, 1958), two membranes having different mobility ratios. The E.M.F.'s of the cells consisting of the mixture of calcium and barium ions to be studied and a solution of known barium-ion activity, separated by the two different membrane electrodes, are then measured and put into the following equations :

$$E_1 = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_{Ba}^I}{a_{Ba}^{II} + a_{Ca}^{II} \cdot \left[\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Ba}} \right]_1} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_{Ba}^I}{a_{Ba}^{II} + a_{Ca}^{II} \cdot \left[\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Ba}} \right]_2} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

With known values of a_{Ba}^I , E_1 , E_2 , $\left[\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Ba}} \right]_1$ and $\left[\frac{U_{Ca}}{U_{Ba}} \right]_2$ the above two equations may

be solved for a_{Ba}^{II} and a_{Ca}^{II} .

In order to ascertain the accuracy with which the procedure measures individual ion activities in a mixture, the determination has first been made with known activity mixtures. The results recorded in Table II show that the procedure is quite reliable for the range of activities used in the experiments. Calcium and barium clays were

prepared by adding respectively calculated amounts of the oxides of calcium and barium to an electrodyalysed hydrogen clay which was a montmorillonite, isolated from a black cotton soil of Padegaon, Bombay. The mixtures were allowed to attain equilibrium in stoppered bottles for more than one week with occasional shaking.

Calcium clay (2 c.c.) was taken in each of 6 bottles and calculated amounts of BaCl₂ were added in each, and made up with water to 30 c.c. The contents of the bottles were allowed to equilibrate with occasional shaking for 48 hours. The mixture was set against $a_{Ba} = 0.0027$ (inside the membrane electrode which is the negative terminal of the cell) and the E.M.F.'s for the same system were measured with the help of two clay-membrane electrodes [K.H. 5 and T.C. 6 (2); cf. Table III] having respectively the mobility ratios U_{Ca}/U_{Ba} equal to 0.138 and 1.257.

The individual a_{Ca}^H and a_{Ba}^H were then calculated by solving the simultaneous equations (i) and (ii).

The relevant data for the reverse reaction were obtained in an exactly similar manner. The results are shown in Table III and graphically shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

TABLE II

Ca²⁺ and Ba²⁺ ion activities in mixtures of the two ions
 Inside $a_{Ba} = 0.0027$. Outside $a_{Ba} = 0.00018$. $a_{Ca} = 0.0005$.

Membrane.	E.M.F.	U_{Ca}/U_{Ba} .	a_{Ca}^H .	a_{Ba}^H .
A. A. C. 6 (4)	-4.0 mV	0.967	(B-C) 0.0005	0.00017
B. T. C. 6 (2)	-3.5	1.257	(B-D) 0.0005	—
C. K. H. 5	-6.0	0.138	(C-D) 0.0005 (B-A) 0.0005	0.00026 0.00017
D. K. C. 5	-4.75	0.680	(A-D) 0.0004 (A-C) 0.0005	— —

TABLE III

BaCl ₂ or CaCl ₂ added (m.e.) ...	0	Ca (clay) ₂ -BaCl ₂						
		20	40	60	80	100	120	
$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	...	1.78	3.00	4.69	6.27	7.85	9.43	
$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	...	1.04	1.90	2.61	3.54	4.26	5.25	
		Ba (clay) ₂ -CaCl ₂						
$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	—	0	1.37	2.64	3.86	5.04	6.27	
$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	—	0.15	0.63	1.54	2.52	3.54	4.52	

For the purpose of evaluating the activity in the clay system, the latter was freed from electrolytes by centrifugation and redispersed in 30 c.c. of water, i.e. the original

volume of the mixture, and the activity of the individual ions in the clay phase was measured as usual. The results of measurement of Ba^{2+} and Ca^{2+} ion activities in the solution and the clay (Pačegaon) phases are recorded in Tables IV and V and the equilibrium constants, calculated on the basis of these data, are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE IV

Activity of ions in the solution phase.

Ca^{2+} or Ba^{2+} added (m.e.)	Ba (clay) ₂ -CaCl ₂ .					
	20	40	60	80	100	120
$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	2.72	5.3	6.6	7.5	8.0	8.25
$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	0.72	1.1	1.5	1.99	2.3	3.01
	Ca (clay) ₂ -BaCl ₂ .					
	20	40	60	80	100	120
$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	2.28	2.99	4.77	6.79	5.84	9.25
$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	0.97	1.49	2.38	2.48	3.67	1.76

TABLE V

Activity of ions in clay phase.

Ca^{2+} or Ba^{2+} added (m.e.)	20	40	60	80	100	120
Ba (clay) ₂ -CaCl ₂ .						
$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	0.76	0.91	1.06	1.3	1.5	...
$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	0.67	0.36	0.49	0.33	0.24	...
Ca (clay) ₂ -BaCl ₂ .						
$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	1.43	0.81	1.9	2.27	1.10	1.99
$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	0.52	0.32	0.64	0.83	0.30	0.78

DISCUSSION

The mobility ratios of some of the membrane electrodes, recorded in Table I, are fairly different and are therefore quite suitable for the purpose of the measurements envisaged here. Of the four, mentioned in the table, only two have been used [K. H. 5 and T. C. 6(2)] for subsequent activity measurements. It will be seen from the data shown in Table II that a_{Ca} and a_{Ba} , determined in the mixtures, agree well with the actual values.

The calcium and barium ion activities in both the forward and reverse reactions show more or less the same trend. a_{Ca} in both the reactions increases sharply from the beginning, but near about the symmetry concentration, the rise in activity is less marked. After this there is again a sharp rise. a_{Ba} , however, increases only slightly at the initial stage, but remains more or less constant afterwards even in the forward reaction in which barium ions are added in increasing amounts. The observed changes in activity are in accord with a greater adsorbability of barium compared to calcium ions.

It will be seen from Tables IV and V that the variation of the activities is almost similar in both the solution as well as in the clay phases. The equilibrium

constants of the forward reaction is more or less constant at low concentration range, but show a higher value at a high concentration of added barium ions (Table VI).

TABLE VI

Case.	Total $a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	a_{Ba} (soln) $\times 10^4$	a_{Ba} (clay) $\times 10^4$	Total $a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	a_{Ca} (soln) $\times 10^4$	a_{Ca} (clay) $\times 10^4$	$K_{calc.}$	$1/K.$
$Ca (clay)_2 + BaCl_2 = CaCl_2 + Ba (Clay)_2$ (vide Table III)								
1	1.04	0.99	0.05	1.78	1.64	0.14	0.60	1.66
2	1.89	1.86	0.03	3.00	2.92	0.08	0.62	1.62
3	2.61	2.55	0.06	4.70	4.50	0.19	0.59	1.63
4	1.54	1.46	0.08	6.27	6.04	0.23	1.52	0.66
5	2.22	2.19	0.03	6.65	6.64	0.11	0.82	1.23
6	2.15	2.07	0.08	8.13	7.93	0.20	1.51	0.66
$Ba (clay)_2 + CaCl_2 = Ca (clay)_2 + BaCl_2$ (vide Table III)								
3	1.54	1.50	0.04	2.64	2.55	0.09	1.49	0.67
4	1.52	1.47	0.05	3.86	3.75	0.11	0.85	1.18
5	1.34	1.31	0.03	7.04	6.91	0.13	0.77	1.13

On the other hand, the equilibrium constants of the reverse reaction show a gradual decrease with increasing concentration of added calcium ions. The reciprocal of the 'Constant' for the forward reaction is also not equal to the equilibrium constant for the reverse reaction, but the difference is not large. This is probably due to the similar valency states of ions involved, in which case 'hysteresis' effect becomes indeed quite inappreciable (Vanselow, *Soil Sci.*, 1932, 33, 95). A similar state of affairs suggested itself from a study of the activity curves (Fig. 1 & 2).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The equilibrium constant calculated above is a measure of the relative bonding energies of the ions to the clay system. If, therefore, a true equilibrium exists and if

the bonding energies of the ions participating in exchange are the same in all ranges of saturation, the equilibrium constant is not expected to vary, as it does, in the above reactions. However, with similar valency ions the divergence will evidently be much less whereas it is likely to be greater with dissimilar valency ions. It should be noted that the calculated activities are very sensitive to the observed E.M.F's of the electrochemical cells.

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